

Human-centred design as part of measuring automotive perceived quality – Extending the product impact model

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Abstract Perceived Quality (PQ) is the current battle-ground for automotive manufacturers. It is accepted that most vehicles today are of an appropriate inherent and measureable *product quality*, so the current competitive edge is sought in tangible, demonstrable *Perceived Quality*.

PQ is directly related to Design and Emotion; the latter is a component in understanding why customers make purchases. Current, mostly commercial measures do not take into account all aspects of a purchase decision based on PQ. This paper looks at a wealth of previous research on PQ and proposes a new framework, building upon recent research looking at product impact, centred upon humans, developed by Delft University.

The perception of quality is personal and potentially very different for each consumer, so this paper sets out to understand how PQ is currently measured in the industry, as what is measured can surely be controlled, so manufacturers should welcome an improvement upon current measures of PQ.

The Product Impact Model makes it possible to access a real-time view of PQ from customers at points of sale, automotive shows, etc. Data gathered via this method will contribute to a better understanding of PQ, including how to measure and control it.

Keywords *Perceived quality, Emotive design, Measurement, Human factors*

Introduction

PQ is arguably a key component of the purchasing process. This paper sets out to define and measure PQ and is intended to follow a series of Design and Emotion (D&E) papers, which culminated in the Model of Product Impact (Figure 2). In order to make clear the difference between Product and Perceived Quality (PQ), these will be defined first, after an overview of product quality Standards. The paper will consider zones of automotive PQ (Figure 1), some currently available commercial measures and will move on to a literature review of PQ and D&E. The paper re-visits the Impact Model and then integrates it with the results of the literature review into a new model of PQ.

This paper aims to consider:

- *What current Literature provides quantitative and qualitative PQ measures,*
- *What are the current methods of PQ measurement in the Automotive Industry*
- *Can a model of product impact centred upon humans, be developed to give greater definition of customer PQ?*

In order to understand PQ better, it is useful to consider *product* quality and some well-accepted definitions follow, but first a look at standards. Today,

quality products are expected from any manufacturer or supplier. Sophisticated sets of objective measures have been developed to assess a product's quality.

Some are manufacturer or supplier-driven, others promoted by magazines or consumer organisations, yet more by national or international standards, for example:

- *Manufacturers – e.g. the BMW QZ (Qualitätszahl or Quality number) system. This is used by in-house Auditors to score a car for demerits, so the lower a score, the better the car is. Many manufacturers use something similar.*
- *Magazines and web-sites – many use a simple five star system, where five is best. This is familiar to those who recognise the star system rating for hotels.*
- *Consumer organisations – Which? uses a series of coloured symbols for instant consumer assessment, such as 'Best Buy', 'Don't Buy' 'Great Value' and 'Worth a look'.*
- *National Standards – in Europe and the UK, many old British Standards have been subsumed into EU ones - EN or Europäische Norm.*
- *The Stiftung Waherntest is a German standard for consumer protection, of which 96% of the population are aware. (Hamann, 2009)*

- *Japan has their own national version, Japanese Industrial Standard, or JIS.*
- *International Standards – the best known is the ISO (International Standards Organisation) and ISO 9001 is the current quality standard for a management system and is often used as a badge to show a company is offering quality products or services.*

The above measures or standards are not strong on cognisance of any human issues. This paper seeks to rectify that oversight.

Product Quality Definitions

Before considering Perceived Quality, there are many different definitions of Product Quality. These mainly centre on specifications and definitive metrics.

- *Does the product meet its specification?*
- *Is it to the correct dimensions?*
- *Is it the right colour?*
- *Are the material properties correct?*
- *Does it perform to design expectations?*
- *Does it meet a Standard?*

A thought-provoking alternative definition from the early days of the Japanese rise in manufacturing excellence (Taguchi, 1986) is, “what is the loss to society once the product is shipped?”

In his seminal work ‘Eight Dimensions of Quality’, David Garvin (Garvin, 1984) ranked issues that he considered defined product quality. These were:

1. Performance
2. Features
3. Reliability
4. Conformance
5. Durability
6. Serviceability
7. Aesthetics
8. Perceived Quality (PQ)

It is interesting that he should place Aesthetics at number 7, when how a product looks is arguably the first impression a potential customer might take. Features, in second place, are also aspects that a consumer can assess early on from brochures or on-line resources. Performance can really only be gauged from product use or experience, so would appear later in most assessments. It could be argued that Durability and Reliability are sub-sets of Performance. Nonetheless, this framework is a seminal piece of work on Quality definition, which does feature recognition of a place for PQ, albeit again with no real human-centred content.

In Garvin’s (1984) definition of PQ, he suggests that customers are not necessarily in possession of all the relevant facts about a product’s characteristics or features, yet have made a hire, loan or purchase intent decision. This is demonstrably true when the product in question is a complex device such as a vehicle, mobile telephone or computer.

Very few customers will be familiar with all the attributes of these products as they are so complex.

Consider your last purchase experience of one of these types of product – were you completely *au fait* with the product, or did a later discovery of unexpected attributes cause delight? Did the product have a ‘Wow moment’? (Gallo, 2012). Conversely, did a lack of expected feature cause irritation? Here is some recognition of the human-centred measures and issues.

Good feature is for example a trademark of Apple products. In “The Apple Experience”, Carmine Gallo (2012) explains that at Apple, Steve Jobs was inspired by the hotel chain Four Seasons and the following innovations, which when they appeared in the early 70’s made an impression on a young Mr Jobs:

1. Individual shampoo bottles
2. Fitness rooms
3. Comfortable, quality beds
4. Spas

Jobs did not invent ‘Wow factors’, but developed sound ideas he could relate to from a hotel chain. He was starting to see design from a human viewpoint. Innovation and good feature is often what the customer seeks in an automotive purchase (Sepahvand & Sanainasab, 2013). Fiat CEO Sergio Marchionne declared in July 2007 - “I want Fiat to become the Apple of automobiles. And the 500 will be our iPod” (Barry, 2007). So many companies relate back to Apple in their expressions of innovation and good design, itself a key component of PQ. While product Quality is more a science or issue of metrology, Perceived Quality strays into the realms of psychology (Bucknall, 2015).

Automotive Perceived Quality – what is it and how is it to be measured?

From the preceding definition of Product Quality, Perceived Quality is linked to innovation, good design, desirable features and principally how it makes the consumer feel. It has been variously described as being “like an attitude” (Ophius & Van Trijp, 1995) but also as a piece of engineering learning from the marketing discipline (Golder, Mitra, & Moorman, 2012).

As Matt Wilkinson (2013) comments in his book, “A bias towards rationalism and quantitative analysis cannot substitute an empathic feel for what will delight the customer”. So PQ may also be seen as being related to the field of customer empathy and Empathic Design to generate emotion.

Perceived Quality is more aligned to how the customer feels when selecting, purchasing and finally using and/or owning the product; the affective emotion of product experiences. As an example, consider the excitement and anticipation of the launch of any Apple-branded product. Once purchased, the Apple experience continues when the product is in the user’s own environment - there are videos on the Internet just praising the packaging.

For Automotive PQ, there are many elements, which are traditionally broken down into three main areas of the vehicle, the power unit bay, the cabin or passenger space and the luggage volume. This applies to all

Figure 1. Some examples of the vehicle zones and automotive PQ elements.

vehicles, even those not of a traditional “three-box” design layout. The principal elements are shown (Figure 1).

Current commercial PQ measures

Having looked at the definitions and standards for generic product quality and then defined PQ, some of the best-known commercially available PQ measurement systems will be shown. The aim is to show that these methods are not showing the whole story of PQ.

There already exist a number of measures of PQ in the commercial world and some are listed (Table 1). It is important to point out that being commercial measures, these are marketed and sold as a revenue-generation process. One of the best-known, the J D Power rankings, have developed over time and have even transformed into a consultancy service that provide in-house expertise to manufacturers. Each market has its own version of these tools, or merely uses the commercial offering as it can be found in its native North American.

The magazines tend to just give simple star ratings and aside from journalistic sensational headlines, provide little in the form of measureable or even comparable emotive statements about cars surveyed.

The automotive magazine-based rankings shown (Table 1) are specific to each market, although some publications and their televisual forebears (such as the BBC’s *Top Gear* brand) are cloned to suit local tastes and cultures (Porter, 2004).

ALG (a Truecar Company) each year surveys 30,000 recent car buyers asking for their ratings of brand quality. Through calculation, the index creates a brand score, which represents the recent consumer purchase.

Using a 100-point scale derived from survey respondents’ qualitative scores, an assessment of automotive brands is conducted. ALG do mention the subject of Emotion in their press articles, but their services “provide OEMs (Original Equipment Manufacturers) with early product feedback and findings that support optimal product launch, packaging and pricing strategies.” (ALG, 2012) This company has supplied consulting services to manufacturers for over 50 years and provides a well-respected residual value service for North American market cars, yet emotion and design is difficult to extract from their output. ‘Data, Analytics and Insight’ are three declared pivotal legs of their services, most of which concentrate on financial, marketing or buying trends.

The J. D. Power Surveys provided by McGraw-Hill Financial are however, the most widely used by the automotive industry.

Methodology

Having seen in the previous section that there are commercially available measures of PQ, the following will give a short review of available PQ up to the current date in 2016. In order to organise the reading, some clear topic areas became apparent and are discussed below.

A review was undertaken of currently available research into Perceived Quality and shows that from over 150 articles, papers and books, 80+ were worth critiquing to provide thesis material. As more was reviewed, an assignment of papers has been made, based upon:

- *Current PQ literature, found in only 5 articles or papers.*
- *The VOC (Voice of the Customer) and its representation, found in 14 sources.*

- *Defining the difference between Perceived and Product Quality, seen across 20+ sources.*
- *The all-pervasive effect of Brand and its relation to PQ, in 20+ written works.*
- *Material that is pertinent to purely automotive, represented in 40+ items.*
- *The need in a Six-Sigma Quality tool sense to conduct an MSA (Measurement Systems Analysis) is poorly represented.*
- *The Control aspect is almost bereft of literature.*
- *A brief comparative look at other industries to see if there is any learning there to relate to automotive.*

A large number of automotive biased papers emanated from collaboration between Chalmers University and Volvo Cars in Gothenburg. These analysed the early design and specification of vehicles in minute detail, (Wagersten, Wickman, Forsland, & Söderberg, 2011) culminating in a PhD Thesis (Wagersten, 2013). This

group of people also usefully compared Japanese and Swedish product development techniques (Bergsjö, 2011). Yet more outside this group also concentrated on body and panel design (Hazra, Williams, Roy, & Aylmore, 2008).

Other researchers looked at detail of design and manufacture demonstrating good PQ by considering certain key aspects of a vehicle's features such as door closing sound (Parizet, Guyader, & Nosulenko, 2008), heater controls (Wellings, Pitts, & Williams, 2012; Wickman & Söderberg, 2010) and even the noise from engines (Nosulenko, Parizet, & Samoylenko, 2013).

Only towards the end of the main reading phase did this author find a number of connected papers on the subject of Design and Emotion and the Human-centred school of thought. Empathic design has been considered and reviewed in a UK study (Barrett, 2010) and some research in the field of HMI (Human /

Table 1. Selection of commercially available automotive quality surveys.

Survey brand or name	Method and markets
J D Power & Associates APEAL (Automotive Performance, Execution and Layout)	Examines new vehicle owners' assessments of the design, content, layout, and performance of their new vehicle after 90 days of ownership. Considers 90 attributes in 10 categories. Considers satisfaction of: Ride, handling and braking Comfort, convenience and seats Heating, ventilation and cooling Sound system Styling and exterior
J D Power IOS (Initial Quality Survey)	Assess ownership experience at 90 days and one year on. Overall Quality Overall Quality Mechanical Powertrain Quality (engine, transmission and driveline) Body and Interior Quality and Design Features and Accessories Quality and Design Overall Design Quality
J D Power DrIVE (Driver Interactive Vehicle Experience)	Considers things that go wrong or fail within the first 90 days of ownership.
VDS or Vehicle Dependability Survey	Considers: Exterior Engine and transmission Sound System and Navigation The driving experience Interior Features/Controls/Displays Heating, ventilation and cooling Seats
ALG Residual Value PQS (Perceived Quality Score)	Active in most markets, including: - ASEAN, Brazil, China, North America, UK, India, Japan, Mexico. (ASEAN is: Brunei, Darussalam, Myanmar/Burma, Cambodia, Indonesia, Laos, Malaysia, Philippines, Singapore, Thailand, Vietnam).
Magazines such as What Car New Car Buyers Survey	POS aims to predict resale values of North American automobiles, derived from Canadian customer surveys.
Parkers Car Reviews	Owners' reviews, plus publishers' comments, with simple, easy to understand good and bad points.
Newspapers, such as The Daily Telegraph reviews and road tests	As above – most markets have similar tailored offerings
Motoring Associations such as the AA Car Buyers Guide	As above

Sources: 2016 websites for J D Power, ALG, What Car, Parkers, Honest John, The AA

Machine Interface) (Erol, Diels, Shippen, Richards, & Johnson, 2014). However, it was these final papers from a cluster around Delft University that finally began to coalesce what PQ is and how to look at the subject from a human and affected emotion point of view. The work in Delft has led to a recent paper on the subject of human-centred design and the proposed Product Impact Model as shown in Figure 2 (Fokkinga, S., Hekkert, P., Desmet, P., Özcan, E., 2014).

This model has been trialled by this author with a growing (30+) sample of vehicle users and found to provide useful data on the emotive aspects of car ownership, so closely associated with PQ and gives a new viewpoint on the measurement of PQ. The importance of emotion in vehicle purchase is evidenced by a BMW publication, which significantly pre-dates the model and makes many of the same emotive connections (Benson, MacRury, & Marsh, 2007). As it is hoped that the research will have some commercial use, purchase drivers are a subject close to the heart of any manufacturer.

Results

The diagram following (Figure 3) shows that the Impact Model (shown by the Design and Emotion D&E box) is a part of the many influences on PQ. It is vital for any company to survive that they attend to customer wants, by using tools such as QFD (Quality Function Deployment) and Kano (Matzler & Hinterhuber, 1998).

As observed by a Swedish industrial visit to Japanese companies, the use of such tools is seen as core to their activities in bringing product to the customer that they want to buy (Bergsjö, 2011). Nissan's own Public Relations machine acknowledges these findings (Sawyer, 2007).

Figure 3 attempts to link the Product Impact Model into a wider look at PQ and is proposed by this paper. It is created from the literature already discussed and the author's 30+ years in the automotive industry.

The results of the systematic critical literature review shows that, of the over 80 papers and works reviewed and critiqued, from a Perspective point of view, the bulk of the research (53 items) takes as expected a User viewpoint, as the subject is perception of quality. There were 10, which were classified as taking a

Fokkinga, S.; Hekkert, P.; Desmet, P.; Ozcan, E. Delft Uni. 2015

Figure 2. Product Impact Model. Source - (Fokkinga, S., Hekkert, P., Desmet, P., Özcan, E., 2014).

purely Engineering view and also a healthy crossover of 17 using both.

In terms of the metrics used in the research material, the statistics do not add up to the quoted total for the subjective (63 sources) or objective (22 sources) and qualitative (70+) or quantitative (less than a quarter), as in many cases there was a clear mix of these. As hoped, there was a strong leaning towards subjective or customer opinion.

Emotion and PQ

A search made on the word 'emotion' in the titles of the collected literature shows only four papers with the word in the title, demonstrating how poorly the current material is at considering and two of these were from the Delft University research group. The latter pair considered "Nine sources of product emotion", (P. M. A. Desmet, 2011) and a summary of Design And Emotion subjects over the last decade (P. Desmet & Hekkert, 2009).

The others looked at the emotion evoked by car engine noise (Nosulenko et al., 2013) and the effect of emotion upon our decision-making process (Bird, 2014). Samples of other subjects covered in the reading are shown below (Table 2), showing the occurrence of the words 'design' and 'emotion' in the text.

Table 2. Literature Review for the use of the words Design or Emotion found in a paper or article.

Paper subject and author	Subject mentioned	
	Emotion	Design
Sound Quality – "Brand DNA" (Abe, Clapper, McCarthy, Rubio, & Schabel, 2004)	2	2
Quality reputation (Cole & Flynn, 2009)	1	3
Seat comfort (Erol et al., 2014)	1	29
Craftsmanship in vehicle interior design (Ersal, Papalambros, Gonzalez, & Aitken, 2011)	1	70
Perceived quality and image (Homer, 2008)	2	3
Door closing sound (Parizet et al., 2008)	0	4
Critical Styling Data (Wagersten & Söderberg, 2010)	0	26
Automotive switch feel (Wellings, Williams, & Pitts, 2008)	5	30

Discussion

Literature statistics

The analysis in Table 2 shows how the researchers whose work has been evaluated thus far treat the subjects of design and emotion. Design comes out as by far the greater concern of many areas of research, with emotion trailing far behind. It is encouraging that the perspective taken by most researchers has the user or customer at the heart of the studies. There appears no shortage of subjective metrics in the material, but little quantitative measure. Planned further work with the Product Impact Model could improve this situation by providing more data to analyse, looking for trends and key words to support definition of PQ.

VOC (Voice of the Customer)

If we accept from the preceding analysis, that Perceived Quality can be measured in part by measures of product quality, then what of the other metrics to give shape to PQ? Traditional PQ is often derived from the ingredients seen earlier (Figure 1). Manufacturers have concentrated heavily on such elements as panel gaps and profiles. This is an element from product quality that is measurable and can inform the viewer of the visual impact of the car. A significant part of PQ, according to Warwick University's WM006 course 'Principles of Perceived Quality' (Warwick Manufacturing Group 2016) is VOC and methods for capturing the same, as well as looking at ways of analysing the emotional effect and the role of all the senses. This is a closed course, open only to one vehicle manufacturer. The VOC section of the Warwick course is based closely upon the work of Professor Noriaki Kano, (1984) whose simple, graphical analysis of customer needs rated execution on the x-axis and their satisfaction on the y-axis.

Professor Kano suggested that:

- *Value attracts customers,*
- *Quality retains them,*
- *Innovation differentiates a company from competition.*

Over time the innovation becomes accepted and even morphs into a basic need, such as has happened with free wi-fi in cafes, or sat-navs and DAB radio in cars and the process is repeated. From a 2016 point of view are dashboard cameras in cars to become the norm?

Kano also proposed that there were three key types of customer need:

1. Basic issues, such as acceptable car fuel economy or comfortable temperature in a hotel room.
2. Performance, such as acceleration of a car to keep up with traffic.
3. Excitement, such as a mobile telephone that integrates well with the car.

Although not a measure of PQ, the use of models like Kano (1984) are vital to understanding the Voice of the Customer and giving it some shape. Other techniques, such as QFD (Quality Function Deployment), much used by Nissan for example (Sawyer, 2007), takes

customer *wants* and converts these into Engineering *hows*.

The Chalmers University industrial visit to Japan showed the vital importance of QFD and addressing the VOC to Japanese companies' success (Bergsjö, 2011). Using Kano and QFD (Matzler & Hinterhuber, 1998) to further understand the customer, quality measures must look at PQ rather than what is normally claimed by the manufacturer (external) or deemed important by Engineering, e.g. standards (internal). External = subjective, Internal = objective (Stone-Romero, Stone, & Grewal, 1997). This is where the Product Impact model adds a deeper insight into measuring PQ. The effect of the ownership or user experience on the human clearly has to be taken into account and the model is a useful tool in supporting this analysis.

From personal experience of 10 companies or marques, the author has seen many different PQ scoring regimes, with each one showing similar roots if not scoring devices as the others. As the subject of PQ has developed, the methods of measuring it have grown from the basic Product Quality issues of:

- *Panel Pressing Quality*
- *Panel and trim component Gaps and flushes (size, taper and consistency)*
- *Access and egress*
- *Operating loads*
- *Storage space*
- *Visual Impact, including colour and trim, brightwork or garnish*

The preceding are still vital components, but the following are now major areas of product differentiation:

- *Cabin Ergonomics*
- *Configurable or adaptable illumination of switches and dials*
- *Crash avoidance and advanced driver assistance*
- *Ambient lighting (a new competitive pitch, more possible with small LEDs)*
- *Touch-screens and mobile telephone integration or connectivity.*
- *The "Connected Car"*

The subject of PQ grows with each new generation of vehicle and the real or anticipated needs of the user - the constant necessity to innovate to satisfy customers. The use of the Product Impact Model to measure PQ gives a difficult subject more shape, with the ability to gather focussed data, fitted into a concise model, as shown in Figure 3. It concentrates upon proven neglected areas such as Design and Emotion.

Conclusions

Perceived Quality is a major competitive differentiator for car companies. Some have arguably realised this and made what appear to be concentrated efforts to present their products in the best possible way to appeal to emotions and a desire for the latest and best.

The current commercially available PQ measures are useful, yet remain the protected intellectual property

Product Impact model as input to PQ

Figure 3. Enhanced model of PQ supported by Design and Emotion - Inter-relationship of Design and Emotion with PQ.

of those offering these products, but are recognised by the buying public. They lack an obvious emotive component.

Examining any Company's PQ measures is not easily accomplished due to confidentiality issues and an understandable desire to protect such matters. However, the writer has had experience of some ten different brands or marques of automotive product and some of these have been alluded to here.

Product Quality is but a component of Perceived Quality, as proposed by Garvin. PQ measurement and perhaps subsequent control can be enhanced by the use of the Product Impact Model, by taking a more human-centred view of a product and the engineering behind it.

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